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RESIN IMPREGNATION OF DECOR PAPERS AND COMPARISON OF PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract

Decor papers is a high quality special paper that is bonded to suitable substrate e.g. such as wood composites, using special synthetic resins. Papers impregnated with a resin have gained wide acceptance as facing materials for industrial grade particleboard. The objective of this study is to determine physical properties of the decor papers. The raw materials were taken from five different companies (A, B, C, D, and E) and impregnated with resin in certain rates. After impregnation, some properties of the decor papers were analyzed and compared with each other. Breaking length, burst and tear indices, air permeability, water absorptiveness (COBB), density and bulk of each decor paper were determined. As a result, the physical properties of the impregnated papers were significantly decreased when compared to non-impregnated decor papers. As resin rate increases the physical properties of the decor papers were also decreased. When the companies' non-impregnated decor papers were compared, "B" decor papers have the best results in the physical properties. Besides, "D" decor papers have lower properties than others. Densities of the decor papers were found to be higher by using resins and thus it improves the strength properties of the fiberboards and particle boards coated with these papers.

Keywords: Decor paper, resin, physical properties

DEKOR KAĞITLARINA REÇİNE EMDİRİLMESİ VE FİZİKSEL ÖZELLİKLERİNİN KARŞILAŞTIRILMASI

Özet

Dekor kağıtları, özel reçineler kullanılarak odun kompozitleri gibi malzemelerin yüzeylerine kaplanan yüksek kalitede özel kağıtlardır. Reçine emdirilmiş kağıtlar yonga levha gibi endüstrilerde geniş bir kabul edilebilirliğe sahiptir. Bu çalışmanın amacı beş farklı (A, B, C, D ve E) firmadan temin edilen dekor kağıtlarının fiziksel özelliklerini belirlemek, bu kağıtlara reçine emdirerek fiziksel özelliklerdeki değişimi tespit etmek ve birbirleri ile karşılaştırmaktır. Her bir dekor kağıdının kopma uzunluğu, patlama ve yırtılma indisleri, hava geçirgenliği, su emiciliği (Cobb), yoğunluk ve hacimlilik özellikleri belirlenmiştir.

Sonuç olarak, reçine emdirilmiş dekor kağıtlarının fiziksel özelliklerinde belirgin bir düşüş olmuştur. Firmaların reçine emdirilmemiş dekor kağıtları karşılaştırıldığında ise "B" firmasına ait kağıtların fiziksel özellikleri diğer firmalara göre daha iyi çıkmıştır. "D" firmasına ait kağıtların ise diğerlerine göre daha düşük fiziksel özellikleri olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Reçine emdirilmiş dekor kağıtlarının yoğunlukları daha yüksek bulunmuştur ve yoğunluklardaki yükseklik sayesinde bu kağıtlar kullanılarak kaplanan yonga levha ve lif levhaların fiziksel özelliklerinde iyileşmeler olacaktır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Dekor kağıtları, reçine, fiziksel özellikler

1 Introduction

The use of wood-based panels, without improvement of the surface appearance and the physical properties, is progressively disappearing. Although particleboard panels are used for interior applications, their hygroscopic structure plays an important role on their performance due to long-term changes in relative humidity [1]-[3]. Particleboard panel products are coated by impregnated papers, paint, print, varnish, veneers, laminates, foils, etc. Lamination is a process that imparts a pleasing appearance in addition to improving the physical, mechanical, and optical properties. The main surface characteristics obtained by the lamination process are resistance to scratching, abrasion, moisture, heat, and to some household chemicals. The layers of a laminate floor were illustrated in Fig. 1. The purposes of these applications are to increase physical, mechanical, and surface properties, to suppress the absorption of water and humidity, and to eliminate the release of formaldehyde emission [4]-[7]. Surface improvement by the lamination depends on the materials used in laminating and the system used for lamination [3], [6], [8]. In addition, the resin type used in the production of substrate and

coating materials affects the final product's properties. As a rule, urea and melamine formaldehyde resins (synthetic resins) are extensively used as binder adhesives in the production of panel and coating materials [9]. For coating of the particleboards widely different materials such as decor paper and synthetic resins have been used. Decor papers are specialty papers used to upgrade the surface of wood-based panels. They are technically advanced and highly engineered products that provide an excellent surface for decorative printing and resin saturation for use in the production of furniture, laminate flooring and other interior and exterior architectural panels [10].

Figure 31. Layers of a laminated floor

The decor paper is based on alpha cellulose. Alpha cellulose is undissolved part of the cellulose in 18% NaOH solution. Alpha cellulose-rich pulp (alpha pulp) is produced by the purification with hot or cold alkali of special pulps containing an easily extractable hemi cellulose fraction. Suitable cooking processes are prehydrolyzed kraft or acid sulfite methods. Alpha pulp must contain higher than 90% alpha cellulose. It is used widely as a raw material to produce cellulose derivatives such as cellulose xanthate, acetate, and nitrate. Nowadays, decorative papers made from alpha pulp are used in laminated board manufacture because of their resistance to photo yellowing [11], [12].

Papers impregnated with a resin have gained wide acceptance as facing materials for industrial grade particleboard and fiberboard. Alpha-cellulose papers are used exclusively as the base papers for the decorative films [3], [10]. For impregnating, papers must have a high moisture resistance and the right porosity to accept the proper amount of resin. The surface print quality of the decor paper is essential, so that decorative designs can be created using gravure printing processes. A sample of the décor papers were given in Fig. 2.

Figure 32. A decor paper used in the boards

It must also be possible to impregnate the paper with the appropriate synthetic resins that can include urea formaldehyde, melamine formaldehyde, acrylic, phenolic resins, and mixtures thereof. The coating is laminated under high pressure and heat with particleboards or other substrates [1].

In this study, it was aimed to determine the physical properties of the different decor papers and effects of resin impregnation on these properties. Thereafter, it was determined how the physical properties had been changed.

2 Materials and Methods

Five different decor paper types with grammages of 50 (g/m²) (printed wood grain) were obtained from commercial suppliers

in Turkey. ("A", "B", "C", "D", and "E"). This study was conducted at Kahramanmaraş Sutcu Imam University Faculty of Forestry, Pulp and Paper Production Laboratory. The papers were impregnated by using urea formaldehyde (UF) and melamine formaldehyde (MF).

2.1 Resin Impregnation

The decor papers were impregnated with 50% UF and 50% MF. The resin was applied to the papers in certain rates (100%, 125%, 150%, 175%, and 200%) and the physical properties of the papers were determined. The papers impregnated with 100% resin was gave the best result in the physical properties (data not shown). Therefore, this rate was applied to all decor papers and the grammages of these impregnated papers became 100 g/m².

The decor papers were impregnated by using a roller brush and impregnated papers were dried overnight at room temperature.

2.2 Determining of Physical Properties of Decor Papers

The dried papers were conditioned at 23±1 °C and 65% relative humidity in conditioning room accordance with TAPPI T 402 om-88 standard. Then, the conditioned papers were prepared for physical tests.

The breaking length (TAPPI T494 om-01 (2006)), burst index (TAPPI T403 om-97 (1997)), tear index (TAPPI T414 om-12 (2012)), air permeability (TAPPI T460 om-02 (2006)), bulk and density (TAPPI T220 sp-10 (2010)), and water absorptiveness (TAPPI T441 om-09 (2013)) [13]. The tests were carried out in triplicate.

3 Results and Discussions

The physical properties of the non-impregnated decor papers were presented in Table 1 in order to compare with each other. Table 8. The physical properties of the non-impregnated decor papers

Decor Papers	Breaking Length (km)	Burst Index (kPa•m ² /g)	Tear Index (mN•m ² /g)	Air Permeability (m ³ /min)	Bulk (cm ³ /g)	Density (g/cm ³)	Cobb (g/m ²)
A	3.1	1.60	3.92	313	1.19	0.84	61
B	3.3	2.16	3.92	308	1.28	0.78	53
C	3.2	1.83	3.92	299	1.18	0.85	52
D	2.7	1.37	3.14	329	1.05	0.95	48
E	3.2	1.96	3.92	290	1.12	0.89	55

Breaking length is generally used in the paper trade to characterize the inherent strength of paper. It affords an excellent basis for comparing the strength of papers made from different furnishes and having different basis weight. Bursting strength tells how much pressure paper can tolerate before rupture. According to Table 1, "B" decor papers gave the best result in breaking length (3.3 km) and burst index (2.16 kPa•m²/g). Tearing resistance indicates the behavior of paper in various end use situations; such as evaluating web runnability, controlling the quality of newsprint and characterizing the toughness of packaging papers where the ability to absorb shocks is essential. Other physical properties of the papers were found to be similar with each other. When Table 1 analyzed, it is clearly seen that the physical properties of D decor papers were lower than those of others.

The physical properties of the impregnated decor papers were given in Table 2.

Table 9. The physical properties of the impregnated decor papers

Decor Papers	Breaking Length (km)	Burst Index (kPa•m ² /g)	Tear Index (mN•m ² /g)	Air Permeability (m ³ /min)	Bulk (cm ³ /g)	Density (g/cm ³)	Cobb (g/m ²)
A	2.7	1.40	1.14	19	1.07	0.94	13
B	2.4	1.37	0.71	8	1.02	0.98	17
C	2.7	1.36	0.73	14	0.93	1.08	12
D	2.3	1.31	0.71	11	1.00	1.00	11
E	1.8	1.36	0.69	15	0.99	1.01	14

"E" decor papers showed lower breaking length (1.8 km) than other papers and the burst and tear indices of "A" decor papers were higher than those of other papers (Table 2). There are no significant differences between other physical properties of these papers.

Figure 33. The breaking lengths and burst and tear indices of the decor papers (-non refers to non-impregnated papers)

The breaking lengths and tear and burst indices of the impregnated and non-impregnated decor papers were illustrated in Fig. 3. According to Fig. 3, the physical properties of impregnated decor papers have decreased when compared with non-impregnated papers. Especially, the tear indices of the papers showed significantly decreases. Increases of the paper grammages by using resin decreased the fiber rate in paper. Therefore, decreases of the breaking length and burst and tear indices have occurred [14].

The air permeability and Cobb values of the impregnated papers were decreased when compared with non-impregnated papers. Resin impregnation increases the resistance of paper against water and air [15]. Cobb has an important role for decor papers due to usage area. Decor papers on particle or fiberboards are giving a good-looking and resistant surface for use as furniture, decoration panels and flooring [16]. Decor papers prevent the formation of nutrient media for pests such as insects, thereby preventing damage to the fiberboards and particle boards.

High density causes more compact and tighter structure. Papers of high density consist of more resin and woody cells than papers of low density. For this reason, high density improves the properties of products such as fiberboards and particle boards [17], [18].

Densities of the decor papers were found to be higher by using resins and thus it improves the strength properties of the fiberboards and particle boards coated with these papers.

4 Conclusion

1. The physical properties of the decor papers such as breaking length and burst and tear indices were decreased by using resin which increases fragility of papers. For instance, the breaking length of the "E" decor paper was decreased about 43.8%.
2. Since resin coated between the fibers and fiber surfaces, the air permeability and Cobb value were decreased about 95% and 75%, respectively.
3. When the impregnated decor papers compared with each other, the physical properties of "A" decor papers were found to be higher. Accordingly, this decor paper can be suitable for fiberboards and particle boards used in indoor applications.
4. When the non-impregnated decor papers compared with each other, the physical properties of "B" decor papers were found to be better.

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